

Allama Ibn Khaldun and Shah Waliullah's Doctrine of Economy (A Research Review)

Muhammad KarimKhan, Muhammad Sarwar, Abdul Rashid Qadri, Azhar Farid, Muhammad Ashfaq, Muhammad Naveed Iqbal, Ahmad Raza

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 08, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 11, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Economy, Doctrinelivelihood,Tax,Sharia Principles</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5562792</p>	<p><i>The Islamic doctrine of the economy is according to nature and is the only solution to all economic problems because it is neither imaginary like Plato's ideology nor based on corruption like capitalism. This system is not based on experience. This is not the result of the mental and intellectual efforts of economists, but this economic system has been given by Allah Almighty and presented by the Prophet of Islam, so this system is the only economic system that covers an economic system of the whole world because the real Lord has made it. He is the Lord of us all. Allah Almighty, along with the creation of man, also arranged for his necessities and taught him the art and craft to meet the needs of his life. The Qur'an and Hadith, like other aspects of human life, describe the economic aspect as well. The basic principles have been laid down for the three angles of the economic aspect (wealth acquisition, use of wealth, and distribution of wealth). A study of the Qur'an and Hadith makes it clear that the economy is an important part of human life but it is not the center of human life. Otherwise, there will be no difference between animals and human beings.</i></p>

Introduction

The greatest and most organized revolution for the human economy was initiated by the Holy Prophet, in which brotherhood was the basis and all forms of interest were abolished in one fell swoop. This revolution also affected the economic rights of human beings as well as animals. The climax of the economic revolution was that Umar ibn al-Khattab, as Amir al-mu'minin, declared in Madinah:

“If a young goat dies of starvation on the Euphrates, I am afraid I will be asked about it”.ⁱ

The economic ideology of Islam has been the subject of research by Muslim thinkers of all ages since the Qur'an and Hadith, and regular books have been written on it. To meet the needs, it is a matter of time when Europe was still plunged into the darkness of the Dark Ages (550-625 AD), the books of Muslim economic thinkers bear witness to this.

Muslim thinkers have written, are writing, and will write more on the human economy from the time of Prophet Hood to the present day. Hundreds of books and magazines on the Islamic economy have been written in many languages besides Arabic, Persian, Urdu, and English. It is a difficult task to cover all the different aspects of the economic system of Islam, so here is a summary of the economic theories of Allama Ibn Khaldun, using the economic doctrines of Shah Waliullah. To described the economic system of Islam.

Allama Ibn Khaldun's Philosophy of Economy:

Allama Abdul Rahman bin Khaldun writes about the philosophy of the human economy:

“Remember! Man is naturally in need of sustenance and his life depends on sustenance from the day of birth to the end. Childhood, youth, and old age depend on sustenance and it is always needed. To survive, one has to run all worldly affairs over the world for the sake of life. He has to work hard for this purpose. Man can never be deprived of sustenance. God is self-sufficient and O people! You all need food. The Allah Almighty created the world and all the blessings of the world for man and He reminded His servants of this special grace in various verses of the Qur'an. He said:

“Indeed in the creation of the heavens and the earth, and the continuous alternation of night and day, and the ships which sail the seas carrying what is of use to men, and the water which Allah sends down from the sky thereby reviving the dead earth and dispersing all kinds of beasts in it, and the movement of the winds, and the obedient clouds between heaven and earth - certainly in all these are signs for the intelligent”.ⁱⁱ

There are other verses in this regard. The world and the corners of the world are in the hands of man as the caliph and he is capable of everything as a human being. There are countless people in the world, but one is capable of one thing and the other of another. In this way, human hands are scattered and one or another human being is capable of anything in the world. If a person takes possession of something, then that thing is unlawful

for others. Unless the owner makes him the owner of the property in some way. One of the most popular ways to buy and sell others is to buy and sell them in exchange for one thing or another.

Therefore, when a person goes through a period of weakness and becomes an adult, he becomes addicted to earning money so that he can spend some of what the Almighty has given him for his needs and pay the price for his daily needs. Be able to buy things. The Almighty said: "Seek sustenance according to the law of Allah." It became clear that men must seek employment. Some things can be obtained without struggle. Like rainwater which is used for many other human needs besides irrigation. But these things are helpful jobs. Despite them, the struggle is needed.

Differences between Sustenance and livelihood:

If a person's income is equal to his needs, then it is called livelihood. If it is more than required then it is called RIASH. Then if a person himself benefits from this earning and spends it on his personal affairs, it is called sustenance. So the Blessed Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: "For you is the same wealth that you have eaten and destroyed or worn and torn. Or sent in the way of Allah". But if this income is not spent only on one's personal needs, then it is not a provision but again for the owner. There is provision for them, provided they take advantage of it. This is the reality of sustenance according to Ahl as-Sunnah. But the Mu'tazilah say that a legitimate possession is also a condition for sustenance. If a person illegally seizes something or seizes something haraam, then according to the Mu'tazilites it is beyond the limits of sustenance, but the Ahl as-Sunnah also calls it sustenance. Because the Almighty, by his grace, provides for the usurper, the oppressor, the believer, and the disbeliever. There is no room for Mu'tazilah's arguments.ⁱⁱⁱ

Man needs sustenance, for which struggle is necessary and man can never be deprived of sustenance.

Shah Waliullah's philosophy of the Economy:

Hazrat Shah Waliullah Muhaddith Dehlavi writes:

"The collective morality of humanity is utterly ruined when they are forced into economic hardship by coercion and they work for bread like donkeys and oxen." Whenever such a calamity befalls humanity, Allah Almighty devises some way or other to save humanity from this calamity and also inspires one of his servants. The destruction of Pharaoh, the destruction of Caesar and Kisra are among the essentials of prophecy on this principle. If human life is considered to be a link in the same chain from its economic needs to its advanced and developed form, then whatever philosophy will be formed for this human life will be complete and it will consider all life as a whole. We will set up a system for this. Therefore, for the collective life of man, there must be an economic system that meets his economic needs. So when human beings are satisfied with the necessities of their animal life and they have some extra time left over from the fog of bread and cloth, then somewhere they will be able to focus on the fulfilment of their higher talents and other lofty jokes. Given these circumstances, it would not be unreasonable to say that a system of thought or philosophy that ignores the necessities of economic life is neither complete nor correct.^{iv}

Economy and its Associate:

Livelihood is the name of the struggle to find and obtain sustenance, but the word luxury is a noun. Because luxury (life) depends on it. That is why it was named "Mahall e Zindagi" as an exaggeration. There are several ways to make a living:

1. Power is also created by extracting money from the possession of others under the auspices of a well-known law because of power. This is called "Nufarm or Jabaya" (revenue, tribute)
2. Halal animals are also caught and sold to make a living. It is called hunting.
3. Pets benefit from the components of their bodies that are used in people lifting is also included in the provision.
- 4 Such as cattle milk, sheep, goat, and camel wool, silk from silkworms, honey from bees, and eggs from chickens and ducks, etc.
5. The production of grain from agriculture and the production of fruits from orchards is also a provision. All three methods are called farming.
6. Man's livelihood is created by hard work. There are two forms of which will depend on hard work or a particular profession or not. If it depends on a particular profession, it is called industry. Such as carpentry, tailoring, weaving, and embroidery. If labor does not depend on a particular profession, then it is ordinary labor or is created by investing in sustenance. It also has two forms. Either buy and sell goods from one city to another or buy and store them so that they can be sold at a profit when the market is booming. Its name is trade. It turns out that there are four main reasons for generating sustenance:

1. Emirate
2. Industry and handicrafts
3. Agriculture
4. Trade

Writers and scholars such as Hariri and others have said that the livelihood of the Emirate is trade, agriculture, and industry. This is also the meaning given by John. The emirate is not a natural way of earning a living. Yes, trade, agriculture, and industry are natural ways of generating livelihood.

Agriculture is the main Occupation:

Among them, agriculture itself is the foremost and basic profession because it is a simple, clean, and natural profession and does not require much knowledge and vision. That is why this profession is attributed to Prophet Adam. You are the one to tell and teach it. You are the first to cultivate, which shows that this is the oldest and natural way of earning a living.

The Second Source Industry:

Industry and handicrafts are second class and it is a post-agricultural profession because it is not as simple as farming and it is mixed and also scientific. It also requires reflection and knowledge. That is why industry and crafts are usually found in cities. Whose status is after the villages? That is why the industry is attributed to the Prophet Idrees who is the second father of the world. He invented all kinds of industries through the revelation of Allah.

The Third Source Trade:

Although trade is a natural way of generating livelihood, most of its methods are based on tricks to take advantage of fluctuations in commodity prices. Although this method is a kind of gamble. But the law has stopped it. But unlike gambling, it does not take the wealth of others for free. Therefore, it was declared permissible and gambling was forbidden. Then Allama Ibn Khaldun has also described employment as an unnatural method.^v

According to Hazrat Shah Waliullah Muhaddith Dehlavi, Dr. Muhammad Din has summarized the necessary researches related to economics as follows:

Here is a summary of the principled points based on which the collective and economic discourses presented by Shah Waliullah depend:

1. According to Shah Waliullah, the first source of light and guidance is the divine revelation of the Qur'an and Hadith and this is the axis of his thoughts and ideas.
2. In addition to the simulated sciences of the Qur'an and Sunnah, he also includes reason and revelation in support of his established theories and presents the principles and conclusions drawn in the light of divine revelation, common sense, and sound conscience as universal and eternal truths.
3. He establishes different stages of human evolution, keeping in mind the natural distinctions of man, and calls the natural conquest of things in the universe by human struggle a natural necessity. Also, know the nature against uselessness and irrationality.
4. Convinced of the different strengths and abilities of human beings, you consider cooperation and collaboration to be the first need of human society. Based on which the family, the neighbourhood, the city, and the country are built and thus the owners of different forces can help each other to fulfill their own needs.
5. According to Shah Waliullah, the family is the first unit of human society. He also advocates for the principle of family cooperation to dominate the whole society. Just as there are a few earners in the family, some helpers, and some just in need of upbringing, yet the economic needs of the whole family are taken care of.
6. The economic concepts presented by Shah Waliullah are a part of his comprehensive concept of religion. You are not convinced to study economic issues separately from religion and morality. The real fruits of the economic proposals he offers come only when religion is introduced as a whole.^{vi}
7. Shah Waliullah does not make impractical or imaginary plans for economic reform, but identifies from the collective needs of man and the historical factors and evidence the elements that play an important role in the material and spiritual rise and fall of society.
8. Shah Waliullah looks to the righteous Caliphate and especially to Umar Farooq for the practical implementation of the Islamic way of life. In his opinion, the race for representation in the society is usually started by those in power, so he is in favor of painting the whole society in the colour of simplicity and equality by making the personalities of the Rightly Guided Caliphs as role models for the solution.
9. He emphasizes the need for justice and moderation to keep human society on the path to prosperity and hold men, women, families, parties, and the government all responsible for the promotion of justice.
10. Shah Waliullah, while pointing out various types of oppression, insists on eradicating all its manifestations and calls the act of cutting off this Jihad for the sake of Allah.

These are the basic principles based on which the economic ideas put forward by Shah Waliullah can be understood and implemented.^{vii}

Man's Basic Economic Needs:

Shah Waliullah says that man is by nature a collectivist. Allah Almighty has endowed him with such innate qualities that he alone cannot meet the necessities of life and the necessities of construction and appreciation. The outside world cannot be isolated and for the gradual development of every human society, it is necessary that the society each staircase was completed in a better way and could serve as a stepping stone to the next floor. Just as an individual's life can be superficially divided into four stages, such as childhood, boyhood, adolescence, and adulthood, and their occurrence in that order is obvious. In the same way, the existence and completion of the first step are necessary for every step of society.

Shah Waliullah writes:

“Even if a human being is born in a forest far from human settlements and has not learned any customs from anyone, he will still need to satisfy his hunger, thirst, and sexual desire and he will need something to avoid heat, cold, and rain. Therefore, gender desire will force him to have a marital relationship with a woman and when both men and women are in the right mood, they will have children and thus many houses will be settled. The need for religion will arise. Eventually, the first consensus will be established. And their population increases, there will be people among them who have high morals, and there will be events that will cause all the evils to appear”.^{viii}

Basic Economic Needs:

According to Shah Waliullah, the first consensus should be called the cornerstone of party life and human society. Even the smallest group of human beings cannot be deprived of their collective affairs. No matter how far away a human group is from cities and villages, there will be first-class collective institutions. In the first stage of this civilization, human beings face the following economic, social, and collective needs which are jointly addressed through beneficial measures in the best possible way:

1. Food:

Getting food is a basic human need for survival. So man naturally pays attention to the following things.

To find grains and vegetables that are in harmony with his nature, then to learn how to use them and cook them to make them organic, then to cultivate them, to irrigate them, to harvest them, and to clean the straw, Learn how to protect and make it edible. Similarly, the methods of cooking the meat, fats of animals, the use of their milk and butter, and the use of plants, are among the first necessities. Similarly, the search for suitable drinking water and the method of obtaining water from canals and springs or digging wells, and the creation of pitchers, jugs, and pots, etc. To protect the water are among the essentials of the first consensus.^{ix}

2. Cattle Needed:

Capturing pets is also one of the first requirements.

Shah Waliullah writes:

This consensus requires that man pay attention to the conquest and upbringing of animals so that he can work hard through them, such as ploughing the land, transporting them to distant places, as well as the meat, milk, and skins of animals and the use of wool, etc.^x

3. Housing:

This consensus requires that man should have a home that protects him from heat, cold (and the effects of the weather).^{xi}

4. Clothing:

The man also needs a garment that can protect him like a bird's hair, whether it is made of animal skins, tree leaves, or human hands.^{xii}

5. Marriage:

One of the essentials of the first coincidence is that man should live a family life and choose a manœuvre to fulfil his industrial desire and to breed in which no other human being should be his partner and adversary are devoid of adjectives.^{xiii}

The Pivotal Requirements for the Completion of Development:

Shah Waliullah says that man continues to search for the best in the light of his physical needs, intellect, and experience, thanks to which human society moves towards the next stage of evolution. However, the journey of evolution can only continue if man's "basic needs are satisfied" in the right way.

Shah Waliullah writes:

“The information and opinions obtained through man's natural morals and scientific experience compel him to acquire the objects of the first harmony in the proper form, and if this does not happen, he suffers from anxiety and frustration. So the physical requirement to get these things in better shape is called consensus. However, the path to reconciliation can only be paved when a person has attained liberation from hunger and thirst and other necessities of reconciliation”.^{xiv}

Explaining the importance of the basic needs of human society, Shah Waliullah says that this is the basic stage through which every community (advanced and backward) of mankind is involved. Therefore, the Qur'an, which is the divine constitution for the whole world, has described in detail the teachings of this first stage. Shah Sahib writes:

And Allah Almighty, while bestowing great blessings on His servants, has made clear in his great book all the aspects of this agreement. Because Allah Almighty knew that there would be people who are obligated to address the rules of the Qur'an and their common problem is the first type of consensus.^{xv}

Its reason is that, this first consensus is the first foundation of the greatest civilization. If attention is paid to the fulfilment of its essentials and needs, then human society will continue on the path of development. However, if an attempt is made to take society to a higher level without paying attention to the needs of the first consensus, it will be doomed to failure.

Financial Affairs of the International State (Khilafat Kubra):

Shah Waliullah's definition of the Khilafah also sheds light on its financial affairs. Similarly, Shah Waliullah has mentioned the income and expenditure of the Khilafah under various headings. For example, one place he says: The caliph can fight the oppressive kings and destroy their glory only when he is very wealthy and has a large army, so it is necessary for the caliph to make peace with everyone and to pay tribute and understand the requisite reasons well.^{xvi}

State Revenue:

Shah Waliullah has discussed the sources of income of the state under the following headings:

1. Minerals and non-Possessive Lands:

Just as all uncultivated lands of the state, auxiliary landscaping, uncultivated pastures, and springs, etc., are permitted for the individual use of individuals, so too can the government use them for collective purposes. Similarly, the government may set aside certain non-property items for the collective good, which would be detrimental to individual interests.

Shah Waliullah writes:

The Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: The ordinary land belongs to Allah and His Messenger, then it is for you from Me. Remember that a normal land is one whose inhabitants have died and no one can claim this land and create animosity and argue to prove his inheritance. When land is like this, the property of human beings is cut off from it and it becomes the property of Allah again and its rule is like the rule of a land that has not been settled at all. Similarly, the Holy Prophet (saws) has said that "the sanctuary of Allah and His Messenger belongs to no one." (Shah Waliullah) I say that since restricting the pasture is a means of severe oppression and persecution of the people, it was forbidden. Accepting the Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) is because Allah has given you balance and protected you from unjust excesses.^{xvii}

Shah Waliullah has also given the example of Hazrat Omar as a precedent in allocating and limiting the pasture for government needs.^{xviii}

Shah Waliullah has mentioned the incident of Abyad bin Hemal Marbi regarding the use of large minerals by the state for collective purposes. Which the Holy Prophet had given a large mine of salt for personal gain. It was then taken back and handed over to the government.^{xix}

Similarly, Shah Waliullah Hakim advises the time that he should settle the barren and desolate land for his expenses and use its profits.^{xx}

2. Fai and Ghnaim:

These are the sources of income of the state which are obtained as a result of jihad and the domination of Islam, Shah Sahib writes about them:

There are two types of money taken from infidels:

1. Maal e Ghanimat: which is obtained after enduring the hardships and struggles of horses and camels, that is, after a regular battle.

2. The wealth which was obtained without a fight, such as a "USHAR" which was obtained from the merchants of the Jaziyah of the infidels, or whatever they gave in peace or fled in terror, such as the wealth of Fai, etc.^{xxi}

3. Foreign Trade Tax:

Tax on foreign trade is also one of the sources of revenue for the state. As listed Mentioned in the quote above. In this regard, Shah Waliullah says that on the one hand, the state needs to keep trade and commerce open. It can also help to pave the way for conversion to Islam.^{xxii}

4. Khiraj and Jizyah:

Khiraj is the name of the rent that the Islamic State receives on its Mamluk land. Which has come under Islamic rule as a result of military conflict with non-Muslims. The Khiraj is related to such lands and also the non-Muslim farmers who do not own their lands and cultivate the lands of the Islamic State are charged rent of these lands in the form of khiraj.

Jizyah is a tax levied on "Zhimmis" living within the Islamic State to protect their lives and property, and it is levied only on men who are capable of military service. Women, children, and the poor and needy are exempt. Regarding the determination of the amount of jizya and khiraj, Shah Sahib's opinion is that the government can adjust the rates according to the requirements of its spics. He says:

The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) ordered Hazrat Mu'aaz (may Allah be pleased with him) to take one dinar or its equivalent from each adult Yemeni cloth, and Hazrat Umar (may Allah be pleased with him) fixed forty-eight dirhams on the prosperous, twenty-four dirhams on the average and twelve dirhams on the labourer. From this, it is clear that the determination of its quantity depends on the opinion of the ruler. Let him do what he sees fit. That is why the life of the Salaf (Initial People) is different in this matter. Similarly, in my opinion, the same rule applies to the amount of khiraj and other matters from which the Holy Prophet and his caliphs have been narrated in different ways.^{xxiii}

5. Auqaf

It is also one of the main sources of income for the Islamic government and has been a significant contributor to the collective development of Muslims in Islamic history. Shah Waliullah leaves the matter to the ijthad of the caliph or ruler. He says:

In lands occupied by Muslims, the Imam has the power to divide them into Mujahedeen and to dedicate them for future defence needs. As the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said about Khyber, he divided half of the land and dedicated half of it, and Hazrat Umar (may Allah be pleased with him) dedicated the whole of the Sawadland.^{xxiv}

6.Luqta (Lost) and inherited property:

Luqta: refers to those fallen properties whose owners are not known. Or the property that once they were Mamluks but now their owners are missing. Similarly, those whose owners die and who have no heirs are the source of income of the treasury. Shah Waliullah writes:

One type of property is that which is out of the possession of the owner. Such as the inheritance of the deceased, which has no heir, and cattle whose owners are unknown, and fallen things which have been picked up by the guards of the treasury and advertised for them, but it is not known, wealth like this should be spent on the common good of Muslims.^{xxv}

7.Sadaqat, Zakat and Ushar, etc.:

Shah Waliullah has declared these properties as a major source of income for the treasury, which is received from the Muslims of the state every year in the form of Ushar and Zakat. These include donations to the following items:

1. Cattle grazing in the forest whose breeding is increasing.
2. Grains and fruits obtained from agricultural lands etc.
3. Trade property.
4. Treasures and cash assets of rich people.
5. Treasures and burials obtained without hard work^{xxvi}.

8.State Costs:

Shah Waliullah has mentioned the revenue of the state or the caliphate as well as the Sharia expenses of all periods. This is summarized as follows:

Khums expenses: Regarding the expenses of khums, Shah Waliullah writes:

So the mall e ghanimat will be divided into five parts and the fifth part will be spent on these places, which Allah has mentioned in His Book. "And know that whatever you get out of the spoils, one-fifth of it is for Allah and His Messenger, and it is for the near of kin and the orphans and the needy and the wayfarer. Therefore, the share of the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) should be spent on the important interests of the Muslims after you, and the share of the near and dear ones should be spent on the poor and the rich, the rich and the poor. There is another option, Hazrat Umar (may Allah be pleased with him) used to help the debtors from the treasury and those who needed marriage. And the share of the orphans was given to small needy children who did not have a father, and the share of the poor and needy was given to them. He should do whatever he concludes and distribute four out of the five parts of the mall e ghanimat among the Mujahedeen.^{xxvii}

9. Uses of Mall e Ghanimat:

Shah Waliullah has discussed the following about the use of mall e ghanimat. He says:

The basic issues, in this case, are as follows:

1. One is to manage the survival of those who are unable to do anything because of upheaval or financial need or being away from wealth.
2. One is to protect the borders by saving the cities from the evils of the infidels by bearing the cost of wars, arms, and horses.
3. One is to regulate civic politics and management by appointing guards and judges, setting boundaries, and appointing accountants.
4. One is to protect the nation by appointing preachers, imams, orators and teachers.
5. One of the uses is to spend on common goals such as digging canals and building bridges.^{xxviii}

10.Uses of Mall e Fai:

And the ruling on the wealth of Fai is that which is stated in the command of Allah Almighty: So (also) is the right of Allah and the Messenger and (your) kinsmen and orphans and of the poor and the wayfarers so that the wealth may not come into the possession of your children; When he recited these verses, he said, "They cover all Muslims." Therefore, the Imam should spend according to his rank and should look after the interests of the Muslims and not his interests. There is a difference in the method of distribution of the rich. When the wealth came to the Holy Prophet, he would distribute it on the same day. He would give two parts to the family and one part to the unmarried. Hazrat Abu Bakr Siddiq (RA) used to distribute to free the slaves according to his need and Hazrat Umar (RA) had established an office. In which the pioneer and the needy were taken into consideration, so the orthodoxy of each person was given by Islam taking care of his troubles, family, and needs. The essence of all these differences is that each one acted according to his ijthad and acted as he saw fit in his time.^{xxix}

11. Uses of Zakat:

Regarding the uses of Zakat in sharia, Shah Waliullah writes:

One type of wealth is the alms that are deposited in the treasury. The right of this wealth is to be spent in such a way that one of them is made its owner. In this regard, the divine command is: "Surely alms for the poor and the needy, etc."

1. The needy People in need: The Shari'ah has restricted them to the poor, the needy, travelers, and those who are in debt for personal gain.

2. Guardians: The Shari'ah has made them dependent on Mujahedeen and revenue collectors.

3. Wealth that is spent to ward off sedition among Muslims or to ward off an imminent threat from outside, and it is done to help a weak Islam who has a relationship with infidels or a deceptive deception. If he wants to give, he is prevented from disbelief by giving him wealth. All of them contain the word author of hearts. Or this wealth is spent in resolving the disputes between the Muslims. The method of distribution among them and how much to start with someone and how much to give are all based on the opinion of the Imam.^{xxx}

Key Principles About Costs:

Shah Waliullah pointed out a basic principle of sharia about spending which is about the needs of each area must be met before the income of each area. So says:

The Sharia wants whatever is in the treasury should be distributed to the people of each region according to their condition.^{xxxi}

The Need of the Taxes:

Discussing the need and justification of taxes, Shah Waliullah says:

Since the ruler and his aides are engaged in national affairs, it is necessary to put the burden of their economic needs on the city, because their status is similar to that of the labourers who are doing useful work for the city. It is necessary to collect property from the people of the city.^{xxxii}

Establishment of treasury:

Shah Waliullah mentions the need for a special treasury and staff for the protection and management of national income:

And the ruler build a house (Bait-ul-Mal) to keep the wealth he receives from the city safe so that it could be used in times of trouble.

Shah Waliullah says:

Since it is impossible for the Imam and the Caliph to collect the revenue from the import and export taxes on charities and merchandise from different regions and go to each region to make their own decisions, their deputies must perform these duties. Appoint revenue collector and judge's.^{xxxiii}

Principles of tax collection:

Shah Waliullah insists on strict monitoring of the tax system and the requirements of justice in this regard. Says: The Imam (may Allah be pleased with him) should keep justice in mind (in accumulating wealth) and should refrain from oppression, anger and should adopt a method of accumulating wealth that is sufficient for the needs of his helpers and harms the people. And the amount of these taxes may vary depending on the individual.^{xxxiv}

Bribery is more likely to occur in tax collection, so Shah Waliullah says:

It is imperative that the agent be ordered to be lenient and strictly restrained from betrayal or bribery and the people be urged to submit to the orders of the agent so that the intended interests can be fulfilled. In this regard, the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: According to another hadith, "Whoever appoints an agent for a given deed and then fasts it (according to the law and regulation), then if he takes anything from the government and unlawful government property, it is treason. Also, in a hadith, the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) cursed those who take and give bribes. The secret is that bribery is against expediency (national prosperity and economic stability) and opens the door to (economic and social) corruption.^{xxxv}

In another place, Shah Waliullah calls the oppression of tax collectors a robbery. He says:

Excessive collection of Usher and Zakat is tantamount to robbery and even worse.^{xxxvi}

Oppression in the collection of taxes affects the whole society and gradually its harmful effects shake the whole country. In this regard, Shah Waliullah has drawn a very eloquent and effective map of the situation of his time.

He says:

The second major flaw of the present civilization is that the government has imposed heavy taxes on landlords, farmers, industrialists, and craftsmen. The obedient subjects are being burdened by these taxes and their condition is getting worse and worse while one class is the one who is fed up with this unjust burden and the violence of the workers and has adopted a rebellious attitude.^{xxxvii}

According to Allama Ibn Khaldun and Shah Waliullah, the basic units of the economy are clear. The system of tax collection including its all associate must be founded on the basic principles of sharia. Man can fulfill his needs. The people of Islam should also build their economic structures on these foundations so that there can be economic development along with scientific development, especially for the revival of the economy in Pakistan. These principles must be adopted.

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Author Information

Dr Muhammad Karim Khan

Assistant Professor Imperial College Of Business Studies, Lahore

Dr. Abdul Rashid Qadri

Associate Professor The University of Lahore, Lahore

Dr Muhammad Ashfaq

Religious Scholar Pakistan Islamic Centre Rotterdam

Dr Ahmad Raza

Assistant Professor Imperial College of Business Studies, Lahore

Dr Muhammad Sarwar

Assistant Professor University of Veterinary And Animal Sciences Lahore

Dr Azhar Farid

Lecturer Punjab College of Science, Fatehpur

Dr Muhammad Naveed Iqbal

Coordinator Al Huda Public School Faisalabad
